

1 **EGFR is a master and transient regulator of transformation.**

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7 We studied transcriptional dynamics of transformation in human and mice. We describe here
8 transcriptional activation of the epidermal growth factor receptor, *EGFR*, also known as *HER1*, in
9 transformation of solid tissues in man and mice. Despite apparent transcriptional repression in multiple
10 oncogenic contexts, we found EGFR activation and not repression was a central aspect of transformation,
11 including in a genetically engineered p53 deletion-induced solid tumor model in mice. EGFR is activated
12 during transformation of solid tissues in humans *in vivo* in cancer resulting from high-risk human
13 papillomavirus (HPV) infection. EGFR regulates or is co-regulated with genes of the Hippo and BMP
14 signaling pathways, and the tyrosine kinase *MET*.
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Results

We measured total transcription *in vivo* and *in vitro* in multiple settings to understand how EGFR influences the process known as transformation.

I. Expression of wild-type Ras in human cells results in repression of EGFR, but expression of Ras G12V does not.

GSE146479: wild-type Ras AALE cells

n=3 Renilla control; AALE lung epithelial cells

n=3 wild-type KRas; AALE lung epithelial cells

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1956	2.84E-04	0.2262	3.6294792	0.8211302	39023.02	EGFR	3238/19751	83.6
100507500	3.75E-03	0.2384	2.8982842	0.6908642	765.93	EGFR-AS1	4852/19751	75.4

GSE146479: Ras G12V AALE cells

n=3 Renilla control; AALE lung epithelial cells

n=3 KRas G12V; AALE lung epithelial cells

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
100507500	2.11E-01	0.228	-1.250939	-0.2846145	1186.9	EGFR-AS1	7973/19959	60.1
1956	3.72E-01	0.222	-0.893309	-0.1984193	60569	EGFR	10736/19959	46.2

II. Deletion of p53 in human embryonic stem cells does not result in EGFR activation.

GSE168752

n=2 human embryonic stem cells (H9)

n=2 human embryonic stem cells TP53 KO (H9)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1956	5.35E-02	0.312	1.931173	0.6018414	316.15	EGFR	2155/19910	89.2

III. Transient expression of dominant negative p53 R175H does not result in EGFR activation.

GSE162341

n=2 MCF10A (*n*=1 wild-type p53 over-expression and *n*=1 endogenous p53)

n=1 MCF10A (p53 R175H)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1956	4.69E-02	0.463	1.987183	0.9195098	5356.62	EGFR	710/14219	95.0

IV. During transformation of MCF10A cells by HRas G12V in vitro, when assayed and analyzed by traditional means, EGFR appears silenced, not activated.

GSE140253

n=2 MCF10A mammary epithelial cells; parental
n=2 MCF10A mammary epithelial cells; HRas G12V

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1956	2.69e-09	0.304	5.9497697	1.8075603	13578.86	EGFR	550/16243	96.6

V. EGFR activation in transformation is evident when comparing p53 -/- tissues to p53-/- tumors of the brain in genetically engineered mice, suggesting EGFR activation is a feature of transformation resulting from but independent of or temporally separated from p53 inactivation.

GSE115840

n=1 GFAP-Cre p53 -/- brain
n=2 GFAP-Cre p53 -/- brain tumor; medulloblastoma

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
1435888_at	0.022163	-4.36	-4.57	-2.48	Egfr	1606/45083	96.4

VI. EGFR is activated during transformation of the cervix resulting from infection with high-risk human papillomavirus, during progression from CIN to carcinoma, but not during progression to CIN.

GSE64217
 n=2 CIN2/3
 n=2 cervical carcinoma

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_1798975	0.00033899	-15.0648296	1.27275	-1.9802023	EGFR	742/29072	97.4

GSE64217
 n=2 normal cervical epithelial tissue; human
 n=2 CIN (cervical intraepithelial neoplasia); human
 n=2 cervical carcinoma; human

VII. EGFR is co-regulated with the Hippo pathway nuclear effector YAP, the tyrosine kinase MET and molecules of the bone morphogenetic protein (BMP) pathway.

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Query genes:

Query Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value	Description
EGFR	1956	-3.2000	0.0036	epidermal growth factor receptor

Coexpressed genes:

Rank	Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	P-Value	%Co-reg transcriptome-wide
4	BMP1	649	1.9550	0.0038	99.98
6	MET	4233	1.9050	0.0002	99.97
15	YAP1	10413	1.8233	0.0004	99.9

Out of 17858 total genes transcriptome-wide

Discussion

We demonstrated here that EGFR is activated, not repressed, during transformation of solid tissues in humans, and that *in vivo*, this occurs temporally proximal to progression to frank carcinoma, and not during progression to dysplasia.